

Making a Net Zero Action Plan (NZAP)

Authors: Charlotte Pascoe, Martin Juckes, Molly MacRae

Achieving net zero will require a paradigm shift in our thinking, requiring everyone to participate, and the net zero ambition to be embedded in all organisational layers and across all research council activities. Learning to make and exploit Net Zero Action Plans (NZAPs) will enable great research to continue whilst we reduce our carbon footprint.

Many of the skills and knowledge that will be needed to solve the net zero challenge already exist within our communities. NZAPs harness that capacity, empowering individuals and communities to realise their potential as agents of change.

Developing a net zero action plan by using the 5W technique.

The 5W Technique

Put simply, an action plan is a list of the steps or tasks that need to be completed to reach a goal or to complete a job¹. A common technique for simple and effective guidance is the 5W technique (i.e., what, who, when, where, why). This creates a step-by-step roadmap that is a sequence of questions to understand the issue being evaluated and help develop an action

¹ Frese, M. et al., 2007. Business owners' action planning and its relationship to business success in three African countries. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, pp. 1481-1498.
<https://doi.org/10.1037/0021-9010.92.6.1481>

plan that can be used for various types of situations². These typical 5W questions are commonly used for action plan development and design³ (Šormaz, 2020).

To use the **5W** technique, ask yourself the following questions: **What** aspects of your work are related to net zero targets? **Who** needs to take action to meet these net zero targets? **When** will these targets be achieved? **Where** can these changes be implemented? And **Why** would these methods/approaches work, or are there any barriers?

The **5W** technique can be used to develop a strategy to identify your potential net zero targets and the capacity of your organisation to reach them.

- The consideration of **what** areas of your work could be involved begins the journey to specific actions.
- By considering **who** needs to get involved, you broaden the vision of all the possibilities of utilising human resources and management to achieve mutual goals towards net zero.
- The '**When**' question encourages you to identify a set of key milestones for the specific aspects of your net zero targets; by doing so you gain a vision of whether each element could be reached in the short, medium or the long term, and what possible time steps each aspect would require.
- Through consideration of **where** these changes can be implemented, you will look into the different sectors of your organisation or broader company involvement to see how widely these changes could affect net zero goals and the community/sector/group these changes will affect.
- By asking yourself **why** you think this could work, you will think about the opportunities that could help achieve net zero, all the possibilities, and the limitations and barriers you feel can affect your goals.

Net Zero Recipes

From the action plans developed within the Go-Zero workshop series, a **recipe book** has been put together with example NZAPs. Examples include implementing a carbon-aware strategy for hardware replacement, implementing infrastructure for power monitoring, presenting power consumption data and carbon footprint estimates to users for spreading awareness of the impact of the use of high performance computing (HPC), and using Research Software Engineers to review codes and workflows.

Furthermore, the 5Ws method has helped identify who needed to take action, whether it is team experts implementing monitoring, infrastructure managers or team developers and communications staff. Important awareness was raised on the 'why would these methods work', whether because of the concrete set of effective actions or the importance of using hyperscale data centres because local clusters are rarely as efficient. The method also helped to identify some barriers such as resistance to change from users due to possible

² Hernandez, D., 2020. 5W2H, s.l.: [Project Management.com](https://www.projectmanagement.com)

³ Šormaz, Anđela. (2020). Social Media and ICTs as Tools for Visitor Flow Management in Heritage Destinations. [10.13140/RG.2.2.14391.65449](https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.14391.65449).

extra work, finance required for new hardware or research software optimisation and the cost difference of more power-efficient hardware⁴.

We can't wait to become experts before we take action to abate the climate crisis. Sharing the recipes we develop for our net zero action plans is an important first step as we collectively act to create the low carbon future of research and innovation.

Supporting Recommendations

A general discussion of the recommendations can be found in section 3.2 of the [Net Zero Digital Research Infrastructure Scoping project final report](#)⁵. A full list of the recommendations can be found in Appendix 3 of the final report and in addition can be accessed via this [spreadsheet](#).

Recommendation 31: Establish and follow best practice in sustainable use of DRI by researchers: ARINZIT

Recommendation 49: Encouraging behaviour change through raising awareness and offering incentives (GO ZERO)

Recommendation 53: Net Zero Action Plans. Actors in the DRI system are to design net zero action plans that focus on community-led initiatives that are achievable and that realise the fossil-fuel downshift (GO ZERO)

Recommendation 86: Training for users on energy efficiency and carbon emissions (ARCHER2 case study⁶)

Recommendation 87: Positive environmental impact from users. Researchers should be encouraged to report their positive environmental impact (ARCHER2 case study)

Recommendation 120: Encourage a low carbon commute to work: User behaviour study

Final Report Section 2.3.2: Carbon footprint examples tables - setting the DRI numbers in context.

⁴Manika, D. et al., (2023) 'Giving Voice to, and Empowering Stakeholders of UKRI DRI: A Net Zero Workshop Series (Go Zero)'. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6787567>

⁵ Juckes, M. et al., (2023) 'Sustainability in Digital Research Infrastructure: UKRI Net Zero DRI Scoping Project final technical report'. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8199984>

⁶ Smith, L. et al., (2023) 'ARCHER2 Net Zero Case Study'. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7788498>